

TABLE 2— $\log K_H/\log K$ VALUES* AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS** OF 2-HYDROXY- AND 2,4-DIHYDROXYDEOXYBENZONIC COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

$I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} (\text{NaClO}_4)$		$\log K_H/\log K$				$-\Delta G$	$-\Delta H$	ΔS
Ligand	Cations	293 K	298 K	303 K	308 K	kJ mol^{-1}	kJ mol^{-1}	$\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
2-HDB	H	12.00	11.76	11.56	—	67.1	75.0	-26
	Fe ^{III}	11.76	11.74	11.62	—	67.4	23.9	144
	Cu ^{II}	9.04	8.95	8.84	—	51.3	35.2	53
	Zn ^{II}	8.01	7.93	7.84	—	45.5	29.0	54
	Cd ^{II}	6.50	6.42	6.35	—	36.8	25.6	37
2,4-DHDB	H	—	8.14	8.05	7.94	46.7	35.2	38
	Fe ^{III}	—	7.90	7.84	7.80	45.5	17.5	92
	Cu ^{II}	—	5.13	5.07	5.01	29.4	21.3	27
	Zn ^{II}	—	3.61	3.57	3.53	20.7	14.2	22
	Cd ^{II}	—	3.23	3.18	3.15	18.5	14.1	14

*Limits of error = $\pm 0.01 - \pm 0.113$ in log scale. **At 303 K.

are spontaneous. ΔH values are all negative, while the ΔS values are all positive. The higher values for ΔS for Fe^{III}-ligand complexes than those for the other three bivalent cations could be attributed to the higher charge on the Fe^{III} ion: The greater the association with the donor atoms of the chelating ligands, the larger is the increase in entropy⁹.

The greater value of $\log K_H$ of 2-HDB than that of 2,4-DHDB (Table 2) parallels the greater $\log K$ values of the corresponding metal-ligand complexes⁹. The nature of bonding and stereochemistry of the complexes are similar for the two sets of metal-ligand systems as shown by the linear plots $\log K$ values of 2-HDB complexes against those of 2,4-DHDB complexes¹⁰. Linear relationship¹¹ between the entropy changes (ΔS) and reciprocal of ionic radii of the complexing bivalent cations indicated that the coordination number of the cations in these complexes remained the same as that of the metal-aquo complexes.

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Polymetallic Complexes. Part-XXI. Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Manganese-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Mercury-(II) with Bis-bidentate ON-NO Donor Azo-dye Ligands

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AZO-DYES exhibit both chemotherapeutic and antiseptic properties and are used for dyeing food stuffs and preserving food grains¹. They are also used as redox indicators². Potentiometric and spectrophotometric studies have been reported³. The present work reports the synthesis of two new ON-NO donor azo-dyes (Fig. 1) and their dimeric complexes with some divalent metal ions.

- 1; X = OH, Y = OH
2; X = OH, Y = COOH

M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Mn^{II}; X = H₂O; M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}; X = Nil.

Fig. 1

Experimental

The azo-dyes were synthesised by the usual method of preparation of the azo-dyes. The metal(II) chlorides in ethanol were added separately to an ethanolic solution of the azo-dyes in 1:1 proportions and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 0.5 h. On cooling, dilute sodium acetate solution was added dropwise with stirring and the resulting solid metal chelates were washed with EtOH and Et₂O and dried under reduced pressure.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are of the types [M₂L₂/L'₂](H₂O)₄ and [M'₂L₂/L'₂], where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Mn^{II}; M' = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}; LH₂ = 1-(2-hydroxyphenylazo)-2-hydroxynaphthalene; L'H₂ = 1-(2-carboxyphenylazo)-2-hydroxynaphthalene. All the complexes possess high m.p. and are insoluble in common organic solvents but very feebly soluble in DMF (5.0–7.2 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) in agreement with non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

In the ir spectra of the ligands, the broad band at ~3 200 cm⁻¹ (OH) lowered due to the intramolecular O–H...N hydrogen bonding. In the metal chelates this band disappears showing the deprotonation of the phenolic OH which indicate their coordination to the metal ions. The ligand bands at ~1 520 (C–O) and 1 570 cm⁻¹ (N=N) shifted respectively by 5–10 and 120 cm⁻¹ on complexation, which indicates the bonding of phenolic oxygen and azo nitrogen atoms to the metal ions. In case of the ligand (L'H₂) the ν_{as} (COO) and ν_s (COO) appear at 1 645 and 1 420 cm⁻¹ respectively and in the metal chelates these bands are observed at about 1 500 and 1 390 cm⁻¹, suggesting the monodentate nature of the carboxylate group. In case of the Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes, the presence of coordinated water molecules is shown by the appearance^{10,11} of two sharp peaks at ~3 300 and ~3 200 cm⁻¹ followed by a sharp band at ~820 cm⁻¹. The conclusive evidence of bonding is ascertained by the occurrence of the bands at ~520 (M–O) and ~430 cm⁻¹ (M–N).

Sub-normal magnetic moments of the Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes are indicative of the presence of π-type antiferromagnetic and ferromagnetic exchange interaction respectively between the metal atoms in a dimetallic structure.

TABLE 1 – ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
		M	N
LH ₂	Deep brown		10.3
L'H ₂	Reddish brown		(10.6)
[Co ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Reddish brown	16.3	7.5
		(16.5)	(7.8)
[Co ₂ L' ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Brown	15.2	7.1
		(15.3)	(7.3)
[Ni ₂ L' ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Coffee colour	16.2	7.4
		(16.4)	(7.8)
[Ni ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Dark brown	15.1	7.2
		(15.3)	(7.3)
[Cu ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Black	17.2	7.5
		(17.6)	(7.7)
[Cu ₂ L' ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Grey	16.2	6.9
		(16.3)	(7.1)
[Mn ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Black	15.1	7.2
		(15.5)	(7.9)
[Mn ₂ L' ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Deep brown	14.2	7.2
		(14.4)	(7.3)
[Zn ₂ L ₂]	Light red	19.4	8.3
		(19.9)	(8.5)
[Zn ₂ L' ₂]	Yellow grey	17.8	7.7
		(18.4)	(7.8)
[Cd ₂ L ₂]	Brown	29.5	7.3
		(30.0)	(7.5)
[Cd ₂ L' ₂]	Yellow	27.3	6.4
		(27.9)	(6.9)
[Hg ₂ L ₂]	Light pink	43.1	5.8
		(43.3)	(6.0)
[Hg ₂ L' ₂]	Red	40.4	5.7
		(40.8)	(5.7)

*LH₂ = 1-(2-Hydroxyphenylazo)-2-hydroxynaphthalene,
L'H₂ = 1-(2-Carboxyphenylazo)-2-hydroxynaphthalene.

The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes consist of four bands at ~8 550, ~17 100, ~19 980 and ~32 200 cm⁻¹, the last band may be a CT band and the first three may be assigned to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), → ⁴A_{1g}(F) (ν₂) and → ⁴T_{1g}(F) (ν₃) transitions respectively, in conformity with an octahedral configuration. An octahedral stereochemistry is indicated for the Ni^{II} complexes with electronic transitions at ~11 075, ~16 350, ~22 910 and ~30 510 cm⁻¹. Distorted octahedral geometry is suggested¹² to the Cu^{II} complexes with a broad band at ~13 350 cm⁻¹. Both the Mn^{II} complexes exhibit bands at ~18 200, ~21 900, ~23 200 and ~27 450 cm⁻¹ suggesting a high-spin octahedral stereochemistry for the complexes.

The esr spectrum of the complex [Cu₂L₂(H₂O)₄] at X-band shows¹³ three g values of 2.13, 2.07 and 2.02, indicating covalent nature of the metal–ligand bond¹⁴. The G-value (2.8) is indicative of the existence of more than one magnetically inequivalent Cu^{II} ions in the unit cell with exchange interactions among the Cu^{II} ions¹⁵. The

R value has been found to be 1.2 which indicates a d_{e_g} ground state. From the above observations it can be suggested that the overall symmetry of the unit cell is compressed octahedron.

The probable structure of the complexes is represented in Fig. 1.

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Complex Formation of Lanthanons(III) with *o*-(*N*- α Hydroxybenzophenonimino)benzene Sulphonic Acid and *o*-(*N*- α -Hydroxybenzophenonimino)ethane Sulphonic Acid

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THE paper describes the results of potentiometric study of the complex formation of trivalent La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho and Er with the ligands *o*-(*N*- α -hydroxybenzophenonimino)ben-

zene sulphonic acid (H_2BB) and *o*-(*N*- α -hydroxybenzophenonimino)ethane sulphonic acid (H_2BE) in aqueous media ($\mu=0.01, 0.05$ and $0.1 M NaClO_4$) at 25, 35 and 45°.

Experimental

The ligands H_2BB and H_2BE were synthesised by condensing 30% equimolar ethanolic solutions of *o*-hydroxybenzophenone and orthonilic acid or 2-aminoethane sulphonic acid in presence of a small amount of piperidine as the condensing agent. The resulting yellow crystals of H_2BB and H_2BE were recrystallised from ethanol, m.p.: H_2BB , 192°; H_2BE , 210°.

The potentiometric studies of H_2BB and H_2BE in the presence and absence of lanthanon(III) ions were carried out by Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration¹ technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti² in aqueous media at 25, 35 and 45° maintaining fixed ionic strengths ($\mu=0.01, 0.05$ and $0.1 M NaClO_4$) using an Unitec DPH-77 pH meter equipped with glass-calomel electrode assembly. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - PROTON-LIGAND CONSTANTS (pK_n^H) OF H_2BB AND H_2BE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

$\mu = 0.1 M NaClO_4$		Temp.		
Ligand	pK_n^H	25°	35°	45°
H_2BB	$\log K_1^H$	4.07	3.83	3.50
	$\log K_2^H$	8.78	8.58	8.24
H_2BE	$\log K_1^H$	4.86	4.45	4.20
	$\log K_2^H$	9.52	9.35	9.08

Results and Discussion

The $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ values (Table 1) indicate the biprotic nature of the ligands. These values decrease with the rise of temperature and increasing of ionic strength in agreement with Hückel's equation³. The values of free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy changes (ΔS°) of the chelates suggest their favourability which are shown in Table 2. A plot of ($pK^H - ct^2$) vs t was found to be linear satisfying the Harned's equation⁴.